

School of
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Project Description and Findings

Increasing Science Literacy in the Post-Truth Era

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Introduction

Science literacy refers to the “familiarity with the enterprise and practice of science” (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine, 2016). This project aims to address issues related to science misinformation by enhancing the understanding of academic integrity and ethical practices in academic research and publications. The objectives of the project are:

- To examine the coverage of topics related to science literacy, including academic integrity, research ethics, and publication practices in the undergraduate curriculum;
- To gauge the level of science literacy within undergraduate students; and
- To develop a science literacy competence framework that can be incorporated into the undergraduate curriculum and information and media literacy programmes.

The project consists of three work packages: (1) curriculum mapping; (2) Focus group interviews; and (3) Survey. The curriculum mapping aims to examine the coverage of topics related to science literacy in the undergraduate curriculum, while the focus group interviews and the survey investigate the awareness of science misinformation and disinformation on social media platforms. A Science Literacy Competence Framework has been developed and will be available on University College Dublin’s institutional repository and Zenodo.

Project Description and Findings

Existing Curriculum/Resources for Undergraduates in Ireland

In the first phase of this project, we investigated if and how higher education institutions in Ireland offer (multi)literacy educational opportunities to all of their students. We reviewed both the curricula available to UCD undergraduate students and the prevalence of (multi)literacy resources explicitly provided by Irish universities. To review the UCD curricula for the prevalence of (multi)literacy education, we conducted a quick scan of the publicly available module descriptors on UCD’s website. Modules that mentioned concepts potentially related to media, news, information, digital, health, and/or science literacy were then recorded on a spreadsheet, and the associated coordinators and academic majors of each module were also noted.

Eighty-two modules were recorded. Research assistants then emailed these coordinators to ask them to complete a short survey. This survey asked if the modules were relevant to topics of mis/disinformation, peer review, preprints, paper mills, retraction, replicability, reproducibility, retraction, academic misconduct, media representation of research, science journalism, and social media. We received 27 survey responses, and eight of the responses revealed the associated modules were unrelated to these topics. In addition to UCD module curriculums, an exploratory review of alternative (multi)literacy resources provided by universities in Ireland was also conducted.

Findings

Few modules were relevant to (multi)literacy education unless they were very major-specific. For example, media and news literacy was only specifically taught to communication and/or journalism students while science and health literacy is addressed only in classes required by medical and/or science majors. While this is not necessarily surprising, it points to a lack of required basic curricula for *all* undergraduate students to learn the (multi)literacy skills necessary to navigate their personal and academic lives. Additional resources were available to all undergraduate students, usually through university library services. Interaction with these resources was all completely optional, and the majority of them were in a self-guided, LibGuide format. Some university libraries offer in-person workshops, however, to advance these skills, all of which were optional. The majority of these resources emphasised digital literacy and skills, although there were overlaps with concepts of media

and information literacy. There was very little mention of health/science literacy resources available for all students in these universities. The digital skills emphasised in these resources were either aimed at use in academic work, or at professional development beyond university. The skill level ranged from basic (such as learning printing basics and Microsoft Office) to more advanced concepts of digital creation and citizenship. Of all major universities in the Republic of Ireland, five universities offered these resources. If a university is not mentioned, it does not have specific information available on (multi)literacy resources (Table 1).

Name	Mission/Provided Description	Details
UCD Digital Literacy Project	“empowers UCD staff and students to develop key digital competencies that are central to academic, professional and personal success and wellbeing.”	LibGuide format, self-guided and optional, provides Brightspace digital literacy courses, some emphasis on critical evaluation of digital information
University of Galway Digital Literacy Tutorials and Guides	“Our carefully crafted resources empower you to not only navigate the digital landscape adeptly but also to thrive within it.”	Self-guided and optional, emphasis on digital skills required for academic work, one tutorial on “critical thinking”
University of Limerick LevUL Up: Student Digital Skills Development Program	“digital skills and competence development programme for UL students”	Self-guided and optional course with some in-person workshops, covers all topics outlined in DigComp
TUD Digital Discovery Tool	“Once you've completed your question set you'll get a feedback report with resources and next step suggestions on how to expand your skills across the 15 areas.”	Self-guided and optional quiz to determine current digital skill set, self-guided tutorials provided on how to advance digital skill set, comprehensive and including critical evaluation, information literacy, media literacy
DBS Digital Literacy Resources	“The rationale of this guide is to gather a range of useful links together which could be useful when integrating digital literacy skills into the curriculum”	Self-guided and optional competency quizzes and tutorials, offering in-person workshops but the webpage is out of date. Focus mainly on basic digital competencies.

Table 1 Irish Higher Education MultiLiteracy Resources

Focus Group Interviews

Six focus groups of 24 undergraduate students were conducted October 2023-September 2024. All participants were between 17 and 21 years old. Study participants were recruited through flyers posted around campus. Interested students were asked to complete a short online questionnaire which included questions on demographics, discipline, year of study, and times of convenience. Focus group participants were offered a €15 shop voucher as an incentive. The study received ethics approval from the university’s Human Research Ethics Committee. The focus group interviews were designed to explore student use and understanding of social media platforms and their perceptions of the knowledge required to critically assess information on social media. Posts from TikTok, X (formerly Twitter), and Facebook were incorporated to generate discussion and stimulate interaction among participants.

Findings

Focus group findings indicate that participants primarily view social media platforms as avenues of entertainment and socialisation rather than sources for reliable information. Despite this general perception being voiced in the focus groups, participants did reveal that social media has become a main source of news by default as they rarely engage with traditional media (i.e. newspapers, magazines, TV/radio). The participants expressed tiredness of mis-/disinformation on social media in general, noting that difficulty can lead to both confusion and apathy. At the same time, participants also noted that they seldom fact-check or report misleading posts and prefer to bypass them as fast as possible in order to continue curating their own information environment. The focus groups revealed that all participants (all considered “Gen Z”) are aware of algorithmic influence on their social media platforms. One key finding was that they have developed strategies to navigate/control their feeds. This shows they have at least a basic understanding of how their engagement affects the content to which they are exposed:

“I wouldn’t engage with it, because engaging with it once will kind of alter your For You Page, and you will see a lot more of it. So I would probably just watch part of it, get the information that he’s trying to convey, and just scroll away.”
(Focus Group 1)

“You could also narrow your feed by reducing your scroll time because the more you scroll, the more information you’re reading. So that on TikTok, instead of going on For You Page, you could just choose your followings and then scroll on that. So you know what you’re going to be seeing rather than being open to literally any information.” (Focus Group 4)

A feeling of deep distrust in social media platform information was exhibited in all focus groups especially as participants felt social media companies and individuals are motivated to post inflammatory/misleading content for monetary purposes. The proliferation of mis-/disinformation is amplified by the low barrier to entry for content creation which allows virtually anyone to present themselves as an expert. However, the sources and legitimacy of science information were seldom mentioned or discussed during the focus group interviews. The participants did not talk about the scientific process, or how information should be verified. Instead, they put a strong focus on the problems of influencers:

“You see mostly all these health influencers, all these you know, nothing to show under given health advice. Why is everyone a nutritionist? Everyone on TikTok is a nutritionist.” (Focus Group 3)

These focus group discussions reveal a complex landscape where traditional markers of credibility are increasingly questioned, and the mechanisms of social media platforms amplify both the complexities and harmful consequences of information dissemination on social media. Participant experiences also reflected a broader social struggle to navigate this “post-truth” environment and emphasise the urgent need for improved media literacy education to combat mis-/disinformation.

Survey

A survey was conducted between April and October 2024. The survey consists of two sections: the first section asks questions about social media uses, and the second is concerned with science literacy (see Appendix I). The design of the survey is informed by the preliminary findings of the focus groups, previous surveys such as the European Union Media & News Survey 2023 and The General Social Survey 2022, as well as recent publications pertaining to science literacy (Alberts, Hopkin & Roberts,

2023; Howell & Brossard, 2021; Osborne et al., 2022). The survey was promoted on social media, posters, and word of mouth. We received a total of 267 responses: 39.57% of respondents were in postgraduate study and 30.64% were undergraduate students. Over 65% of responses were from the College of Social Sciences and Law, University College Dublin.

Findings

The responses regarding social media use show that over 80% of the respondents had used WhatsApp, YouTube, and Instagram in the last seven days, in which 75.96% of respondents had looked for information about healthy lifestyle and 58.8% had looked for information about anxiety, stress, and similar problems. Over 40% of participants read news that appear on online social networks most often. The majority (76.5%) thought that the written press and public TV and radio stations were the most trustworthy news sources, while some mentioned social media influencers (5.56%), social media groups (5.13%), and blogs and podcasts (5.56%). In the survey, respondents were specifically asked to evaluate the reliability of news reports involving scientific terms including preprint, reproducibility, and sponsored research (Figure 1):

Views on the reliability of research findings in preprint

A new scientific finding was reported: Scientists in Germany claim to have cracked the cause of the rare blood clots linked to the Oxford/AstraZeneca and Johnson & Johnson coronavirus vaccines and believe the jabs could be tweaked to stop the reaction happening altogether, Prof Marschalek and other scientists said in a preprint paper released on Wednesday. Considering the findings were reported in a preprint paper, do you think the research findings are reliable?

Views on the reliability of findings in sponsored research

A new scientific finding was reported: The research into methane leakage has been funded by UK research councils and agencies as well as firms involved in oil and gas exploration and fracking including Shell, Chevron, Ineos and Centrica. Considering the funding of the research study, do you think the research findings are reliable?

Views on the reliability of scientific results that could NOT be replicated

A new scientific finding was reported in the news: In November 2018 news broke via YouTube that He Jiankui, then a professor at Southern University of Science and Technology in Shenzhen, China had created the world's first gene-edited babies from two embryos. Sean Harrison at the University of Bristol tried and failed to replicate the result using the UK Biobank data. Considering the results could not be replicated, do you think the results reported by He Jiankui is reliable?

Figure 1 Survey responses to the reliability of scientific claims

Further, the survey asked two follow-up questions about preprints and retraction. The responses show that these terms are not well understood (Table 2).

	Percentage of responses
Research articles can be retracted because (tick all that apply):	
The research findings are not reproducible	63.16%
The research findings are based on fabricated data	83.25%
The research findings are out of date	38.28%
Don't know	11%
Which one of the following is the most accurate?	
Preprints are more reliable than peer reviewed articles	4.83%
Preprints are as reliable as peer reviewed articles	10.63%
Peer reviewed articles are more reliable than preprints	84.54%

Table 2 Retracted articles and preprints

While these responses do not provide conclusive results about respondents' science literacy, they indicate that more can be done to enhance the understanding of vocabularies related to scientific norms, practices, values and publication process, and that instruments can be developed to assess different levels of science literacy.

Summary

The project provides a snapshot of the current state of science literacy in University College Dublin, including the coverage of science literacy in undergraduate curriculum, experience of science misinformation and disinformation on social media, and the understanding of some concepts in science literacy. The findings shed light on the need for incorporating science literacy concepts in university teaching and information literacy programmes. Most recently, Marcia McNutt (2024), President of the National Academy of Sciences, calls for better understanding of the norms and values of science to rebuild public trust, while Holden Thorp (2024), the editor-in-chief of *Science*, calls for the teaching of philosophy of science, highlighting the core components of science literacy regarding the norms, values, and practices of science. A Science Literacy Competence Framework has been developed based on the research findings and recent publications (Howell & Brossard, 2021; Ma, 2024; Osborne et al., 2022) and will be available on Zenodo shortly.

Acknowledgements

This project is funded by the HEA from SATLE Funding (Strategic Alignment of Teaching and Learning Enhancement) administered by the National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning.

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